

In-Depth Analysis of Demographic Trends and Clinical Profiles of Allergic Rhinitis Patients at a Tertiary Care FacilityRagini Raina¹, Vijay Kumar², Satish Kumar³¹SMO, Sadar Hospital, Arwal, Bihar, India²Assistant Professor, Department of ENT, E.S.I.C. Medical College & Hospital, Bihta, Patna, Bihar, India³Professor, Department of ENT, E.S.I.C. Medical College & Hospital, Bihta, Patna, Bihar, India

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

This cross-sectional study explores the demographic and clinical characteristics of 100 patients with allergic rhinitis at ESIC Medical College Hospital, Bihta, Patna, from April 2023 to April 2024. The results highlight a significant prevalence in the urban population, predominantly among adults aged 25-45 years. Key findings include the chronic nature of symptoms, such as nasal congestion and sneezing, with severe impacts on daily activities and sleep. Seasonal symptom peaks in spring and autumn suggest the influence of environmental allergens. Treatment patterns indicate a reliance on antihistamines and intranasal corticosteroids, with a notable presence of comorbid atopic conditions. This study underscores the need for tailored management strategies to improve patient outcomes and quality of life.

Keywords: Allergic Rhinitis, Demographic Characteristics, Seasonal Variations, Treatment Patterns.

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Introduction

Allergic rhinitis, a prevalent inflammatory disorder of the nasal mucosa, is triggered by allergens such as pollen, dust, and animal dander, leading to symptoms like sneezing, nasal congestion, and rhinorrhea [1,2]. This condition significantly affects the quality of life, productivity, and overall health of sufferers. The global prevalence and impact of allergic rhinitis underscore the necessity for continuous research to understand its demographic and clinical patterns thoroughly [3,4].

This study aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of the demographic trends and clinical characteristics of patients diagnosed with allergic rhinitis at a tertiary care center [5]. By examining a diverse patient population, this research seeks to identify common demographic factors such as age, gender, socioeconomic status, and environmental exposures that correlate with the incidence and severity of allergic rhinitis. Additionally, the study explores the clinical manifestations and comorbidities associated with the condition, providing insights that could guide tailored treatment strategies [6,7].

Understanding these patterns will not only enhance the management of allergic rhinitis but also contribute to the development of targeted interventions and policies to mitigate its impact. This research will employ a combination of retrospective reviews and prospective observations to ensure a comprehensive dataset that supports

robust conclusions and recommendations for clinical practice [8,9].

Methodology

Study Design: This study adopts a cross-sectional design to analyze the demographic and clinical characteristics of allergic rhinitis patients at ESIC Medical College Hospital, Bihta, Patna.

Sample Size: The study will include a total of 100 patients diagnosed with allergic rhinitis, ensuring sufficient power to identify significant associations and trends within the data.

Study Duration: The data collection phase of the study is scheduled from April 2023 to April 2024. This duration allows for the accumulation of data across different seasons, providing insights into seasonal variations in allergic rhinitis presentations.

Study Setting: The study will be conducted at ESIC Medical College Hospital, Bihta, Patna. This tertiary care center is chosen for its comprehensive healthcare facilities and the diverse demographic characteristics of its patient population, which can provide a representative sample of allergic rhinitis patients in the region.

Data Collection Methods: Participants will be selected based on a diagnosis of allergic rhinitis confirmed by an ENT specialist at the hospital. The data collection will involve:

- **Demographic Data:** Age, gender, socioeconomic status, and detailed personal and family medical history will be recorded using a standardized questionnaire.
- **Clinical Data:** Information on the severity of symptoms, duration of symptoms, treatment history, and any comorbid conditions will be collected through patient interviews and medical record reviews.

Sampling Technique: Patients will be consecutively enrolled as they visit the ENT outpatient department, provided they meet the inclusion criteria and consent to participate in the study. The inclusion criteria include patients with a confirmed diagnosis of allergic rhinitis, regardless of age and gender.

Statistical Analysis: Data will be analyzed using statistical software. Descriptive statistics will be used to summarize demographic and clinical characteristics. Chi-square tests for categorical variables and t-tests for continuous variables will be employed to explore associations between demographic factors and allergic rhinitis characteristics. A p-value of less than 0.05 will be considered statistically significant.

Results

The study sample comprised 100 patients diagnosed with allergic rhinitis, with an almost equal gender distribution (52% male and 48% female). The age range of participants was broad, from 6 to 65 years, with a median age of 32 years. Most participants (70%) were from urban areas, reflecting the catchment area of the ESIC Medical College Hospital. The demographic analysis also highlighted a higher prevalence of allergic rhinitis

among individuals in the 25-45-year age group, constituting 45% of the study population.

Clinical Characteristics

- **Symptom Severity and Duration:** The majority of patients (60%) reported moderate symptoms, while 25% described severe symptoms and 15% had mild symptoms. Chronic symptoms lasting more than a year were reported by 55% of the patients.
- **Common Symptoms:** The most frequently reported symptoms were nasal congestion (90%), sneezing (85%), and rhinorrhea (80%). Itchy eyes and throat were also commonly reported, affecting approximately 65% and 60% of the patients, respectively.
- **Treatment Patterns:** About 80% of the patients were on antihistamines, 50% used intranasal corticosteroids, and 30% had tried immunotherapy. Notably, patients with severe symptoms were more likely to have used multiple treatment modalities.
- **Comorbidities:** The presence of other atopic disorders was significant, with 40% of patients having asthma, 25% having eczema, and 20% reporting food allergies.

A seasonal trend in symptom exacerbation was observed, with a peak in symptoms during the spring (40%) and autumn (30%) months. These findings are consistent with the increase in pollen and other allergens during these periods. The impact of allergic rhinitis on daily activities was profound, with 70% of patients reporting moderate to severe interference with their daily work and leisure activities. Sleep disturbances were reported by 65% of the patients, further underlining the condition's impact on quality of life.

Table 1: This table synthesizes the data into an easily digestible format, highlighting the distribution of demographic and clinical characteristics, treatment patterns, and the socioeconomic impact of allergic rhinitis among the study population.

Characteristic	Total (N=100)	Details
Gender		Male: 52% (52) Female: 48% (48)
Age Range	6 - 65 years	Median Age: 32 years
Area of Residence		Urban: 70% (70) Rural: 30% (30)
Age Group Prevalence		25-45 years: 45% (45)
Symptom Severity		Mild: 15% (15) Moderate: 60% (60) Severe: 25% (25)
Symptom Duration		> 1 year: 55% (55)
Common Symptoms		Nasal Congestion: 90% (90) Sneezing: 85% (85) Rhinorrhea: 80% (80) Itchy Eyes: 65% (65) Itchy Throat: 60% (60)
Treatment Usage		Antihistamines: 80% (80) Intranasal Corticosteroids: 50% (50) Immunotherapy: 30% (30)
Comorbidities		Asthma: 40% (40) Eczema: 25% (25) Food Allergies: 20% (20)
Seasonal Symptom Peak		Spring: 40% (40) Autumn: 30% (30)
Impact on Daily Activities		Moderate to Severe: 70% (70)
Sleep Disturbances	65% (65)	

Discussion

The findings from this study illustrate the significant burden of allergic rhinitis among patients attending ESIC Medical College Hospital, Bihta, Patna. The demographic data reveal a predominant occurrence in urban residents, particularly affecting adults aged 25 to 45 years. This suggests environmental and lifestyle factors typical of urban settings may contribute to the prevalence of allergic rhinitis in this age group [10,11,12].

Clinically, the persistence of symptoms, notably nasal congestion, sneezing, and rhinorrhea, underscores the chronic nature of allergic rhinitis and its impact on patient quality of life. The high rate of symptom severity reported aligns with the substantial use of multiple treatment modalities, including antihistamines and intranasal corticosteroids [13,14]. The prevalence of comorbid atopic conditions like asthma and eczema further complicates the clinical picture, necessitating a multifaceted approach to management that addresses both allergic rhinitis and its associated conditions [15].

Seasonal variations in symptom exacerbation, particularly during spring and autumn, reflect the typical allergen sensitivities and emphasize the need for seasonally adjusted therapeutic strategies. Moreover, the profound impact on daily activities and sleep disturbances reported by a majority of patients highlights the broader socio-economic implications of allergic rhinitis, affecting not only health but also productivity and well-being [16,17].

These findings advocate for enhanced patient education on environmental control strategies and adherence to prescribed treatments. They also point to the potential benefits of personalized medicine approaches, possibly incorporating newer therapeutic agents and allergen immunotherapy, to improve outcomes for patients with allergic rhinitis. This study lays a foundation for future research to explore deeper into the environmental factors and genetic predispositions that may influence the prevalence and severity of allergic rhinitis in the population served by this tertiary care center [18,19,20].

Conclusion

The study conducted at ESIC Medical College Hospital, Bihta, Patna, provides valuable insights into the demographic and clinical characteristics of allergic rhinitis, revealing a significant impact on the urban adult population, particularly those aged 25 to 45 years. The high prevalence of chronic symptoms and associated comorbid conditions highlights the need for comprehensive management strategies tailored to individual patient profiles and environmental influences. Seasonal fluctuations in

symptoms emphasize the importance of adapting treatment plans according to allergen exposure. Overall, the results underscore the necessity for heightened awareness and improved therapeutic interventions to enhance quality of life and reduce the socioeconomic burden posed by allergic rhinitis. This research not only enhances our understanding of allergic rhinitis within this demographic but also sets the stage for future studies aimed at developing more effective, personalized treatment and management strategies.

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